

1 Do you feel you have enough football equipment to coach well?



2 Do you feel you know enough about football coaching to coach well?



3 Do you feel you know enough to talk to young people about health and HIV?



4 Do you feel you can combine messages about HIV with football games?



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11 Do you feel you know enough to talk to young people about health and HIV?



12 Do you feel you can combine messages about HIV with football games?

